

O-060 - Constraining Tsunamigenic Earthquake Sources: Integrating Array Seismological Methods with the W-Phase Solution for Improved Far-Field Tsunami Warning

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Abstract: Tsunami early warning systems are dependent on seismic data and ocean height observations. The Southwest Pacific subduction zones lack a dense offshore network of DART buoys and limited proximal seismic stations (and land to deploy them on) making it necessary to use seismic data at greater distances to quickly constrain the tsunami source. This study, which is part of the R-CET (Rapid Characterization of Earthquakes and Tsunami) project led by GNS Science aims to improve near real-time seismological analysis of regional tsunamigenic earthquakes posing tsunami hazard for Southwest Pacific countries. This will be achieved through the use of the New Zealand seismic network, which has recently been enhanced with new broadband Northland (R-CET) stations. Traditionally, seismic-based tsunami warning methods have relied on earthquake point-source locations, which are too simplistic for large ($M_w > 7.5$) tsunamigenic earthquakes. Recent efforts have attempted to relate the W-Phase solution to the rupture area using magnitude-to-fault-dimension scaling relations. However, these relations cannot precisely distinguish the compactness of the rupture (e.g., Tohoku 2011 and Sumatra 2004 earthquakes). To overcome this challenge, a seismological array-based tsunami warning procedure is performed to provide direct spatio-temporal observations of the rupture area for a tsunamigenic source. Two different array processing techniques, the standard FK and MUSIC (Multiple Signal Classification) analysis, were applied to seismic recordings from a recent tsunamigenic earthquake ($M_w 7.7$) in the Vanuatu region, the Loyalty Islands, on May 19, 2023. The results were validated against the post-processing estimates of the finite fault solution for this event reported by the USGS. The utility of this analysis in tsunami forecasts was also compared by threat maps generated from the array source and initial response maps used in real-time response on the day. A comparison was also made with the actual tsunami observations by DART and coastal gauges. The analysis demonstrates the potential to improve initial tsunami forecasts for hazard management before the onset of tsunami waves at deep ocean tsunamimeters through array-based tsunami warning.

Keywords: Tsunami Early Warning Systems, Scaling Relations, Array-Based Tsunami, Spatio-Temporal Rupture

